

band of weak intensity at 1100 nm in the reflectance spectra of $\text{Co(L)O.5H}_2\text{O}$ are due to $d \rightarrow d$ transitions, characteristic of square-planar geometry⁶. $\text{Ni(L)O.5H}_2\text{O}$ has a broad medium intensity band at 710 nm which is assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition, typical of square-planar Ni^{2+} complex⁶. The absorption bands of strong intensities around 490, 720 and 1100 nm in the reflectance spectra of Ni^{2+} halide complexes are assigned to transitions, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$ respectively. These bands are characteristic of octahedral stereochemistry around the Ni^{2+} ion⁶.

The broad bands of medium intensities or distinct shoulders due to ν_{OH} around 3550 cm^{-1} in the ir spectra of all the complexes except those of Zn(L) , $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Zn(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2]$ (where $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) indicate the presence of water molecules in them⁹. The strong intensity bands around 3300 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligand and the complexes may be assigned to ν_{NH} stretching modes of NH_2 and NH groups⁹. The broad band of very strong intensity at 3160 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum can be assigned to stretching mode of hydrogen bonded OH group⁹. In the spectra of the Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Zn^{2+} complexes of general formula $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$, this band is not present which indicates the displacement of hydroxy proton by the respective metal ion during complexation. The absence of any band in the region $2650-2500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand spectrum indicates that there is no SH group in the free ligand in the solid state⁹. The ligand band at 1575 cm^{-1} due to azomethine stretch⁸ shifted to lower wave number by about $10-15\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the complexes. This indicates the coordination of the ligand through this nitrogen in all the complexes. A medium intensity band at 850 cm^{-1} in the ligand spectrum may be attributed to pure $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$. In the spectra of $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$ complexes this band disappears and a new band appears around 680 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{S}$ region)⁸. The large shift of this band to lower frequency in these complexes is the strongest evidence for coordination through the sulphur atom of $\text{HN}-\text{C}=\text{S}$ group of the ligand after enolisation to $\text{N}=\text{C}-\text{SH}$ and deprotonation⁸. In all other complexes the $\text{C}=\text{S}$ stretching band shifted to lower frequency region (around 770 cm^{-1}) indicating coordination through thiocarbonyl sulphur ($\text{C}=\text{S}$) without enolisation¹⁰. The medium intensity bands at $625-600$ and $505-495\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ respectively.

The thermogravimetric studies of the complexes clearly indicate that the associated water molecules were the lattice-held ones as they were lost around 120° . The complexes containing no water molecules i.e. Zn(L) , $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Zn(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2]$ (where, $\text{X}=\text{Cl}$ or Br) are stable at 200° .

Thus on the basis of the foregoing discussion it is inferred that the ligand coordinates with the central metal ion in three different ways, such as

(i) bivalent (L^{2-}) tridentate, as in the complexes of general formula $\text{M(L).nH}_2\text{O}$, (ii) neutral tridentate, as in $[\text{Fe(LH}_2\text{)Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Ni(LH}_2\text{)}_2\text{X}_2.2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and (iii) neutral bidentate, as in the halogeno complexes of Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Hg^{2+} .

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Prof. C. G. R. Nair and Prof. K. T. R. Varma, Heads of the Departments of Chemistry, University of Kerala and Calicut respectively for encouragement.

References

1. B. H. PATEL, J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 9.
2. M. S. PATIL and J. R. SHAH, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1981, 90, 147.
3. M. S. PATIL and J. R. SHAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 944.
4. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
5. M. F. TWEDLE and L. J. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 98, 4824.
6. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1980.
7. C. J. BULLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962.
8. K. K. ARAVINDAKSHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1987, 26, 241.
9. L. J. BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Chapman and Hall, London, 1978.
10. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, B. T. GOWDA and A. S. A. MURTHY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 985.

Thermodynamics of Transport of Water Across Different Cation-saturated Kaolinite Clay

S. K. SANYAL* and A. BHATTACHARJYA

Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

Manuscript received 7 December 1987, revised 9 December 1988, accepted 18 March 1989

REPORTS on studies of thermal diffusion of water in soil¹⁻⁴ are available although the qualitative aspects of the latter received scant attention. More recently, Sanyal *et al.*⁵⁻⁷ re-examined the thermodynamic theories of thermal diffusion and pointed out the significance of heat and entropy of transport in characterising the soil-moisture interactions. The present paper extends these ideas to diffusional transport of water across clays and examines the findings in the light of clay-water interactions.

Experimental

The clays used were kaolinite in K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} -saturated form. They were prepared by converting the crude kaolinite clay to H^+ -form by treating it with 0.05 M HCl , followed by removal of the excess chloride on dialysis through cellophane

membrane and subsequent transformation of H⁺-clays to the K⁺, Ca²⁺ or Mg²⁺-forms by repeated leaching with 2 M KCl, CaCl₂ or MgCl₂ solution, respectively. The clays were then washed nearly free of chloride with distilled water and finally dialysed.

The cell used was the same as that employed earlier⁷. It consisted of a rectangular perspex box, in which the central clay chamber was sandwiched between two terminal water chambers by means of two porous ceramic plates. The two terminal chambers were fitted with two short U-tubes connected to capillary tubes (graduated) through standard joints. The cell was kept covered by means of a perspex lid which allowed the limb of one short separating funnel to pass through an air-tight hole into each terminal chamber.

The three clays, moistened to the corresponding full water holding capacity, were taken in the central clay chamber one after another by maintaining an uniform bulk density of 1.00 g cm⁻³ in each case. While filling the terminal chambers with double-distilled water, due care was taken to eliminate entrapped air bubbles. The whole set-up was placed inside an air thermostat, maintained at the mean temperature of the experiment. On applying the appropriate temperature gradient across the clay chamber, temperatures on both sides of each ceramic plate were continuously monitored with the help of suitably placed copper-constantan thermocouples. The attainment of the steady state was indicated by the water levels in the two short U tubes (which led to ΔP values, after due allowance being made for the unequal thermal expansion of water in the two terminal chambers) becoming stationary. Such thermal diffusion experiments were performed at a number of mean temperatures in a manner as described above, and the corresponding heat of transport ($\hat{Q}_w$) and the heat capacity of transport ($\hat{C}_w$) of the clay-water were evaluated by measuring the steady state hydro-

static pressure difference (ΔP) between the terminal water chambers under a given temperature difference (ΔT) at a particular mean temperature (T). $\hat{Q}_w$ and $\hat{C}_w$ were calculated by using the well-known relations (equations 1 and 2) based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics^{6,8,9},

$$\hat{Q}_w = -\bar{V}T \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta T} \right)_{s,t} \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{C}_w = \frac{\delta \hat{Q}_w}{\delta T} - \frac{\hat{Q}_w}{T} \quad (2)$$

where, $\bar{V}$ is the partial molal volume of water, T the mean (absolute) temperature, and $(\Delta P/\Delta T)_{s,t}$ refers to the hydrostatic pressure difference between the two terminal water chambers per unit difference of temperature at the steady state. $\hat{C}_w$ at 35° was calculated by noting the appropriate slope of the plot of $\hat{Q}_w$ vs T .

Results and Discussion

The values of the heat of transport ($\hat{Q}_w$) and the heat capacity of transport ($\hat{C}_w$) of water for potassium kaolinite, calcium kaolinite and magnesium kaolinite are presented in Table I. The corresponding standard deviations for experiments conducted under identical conditions are given within parenthesis below the appropriate $\hat{Q}_w$ value. In all the cases $\hat{Q}_w$ values are positive indicating an absorption of heat behind and a liberation ahead of the diffusing clay-water⁸. This finds an interpretation in the partial breakdown of the longrange cooperative hydrogen bonding, characterising the bulk water, in course of its passage through the intervening clay chamber owing to the occurrence of interspersed clay particles. The concomitant increase in entropy of the diffusing water in contact with clay particles will obviously be the lowest for the Mg-form and the highest for the K-form of kaolinite, the ionic potential of the cations being in the order, Mg²⁺ > Ca²⁺ > K⁺. Thus, Mg²⁺ should

TABLE I - HEAT OF TRANSPORT AND HEAT CAPACITY OF TRANSPORT OF WATER ACROSS KAOLINITE CLAY IN DIFFERENT CATIONIC FORMS

Clay sample	Mean temp. (T)	$\Delta T/\text{deg}$	$\Delta P = (h_H - h_C)$ cm	$\bar{V}$ ml mol ⁻¹	$\hat{Q}_w$ J mol ⁻¹	$\hat{C}_w$ (at 35°) J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Potassium kaolinite	307.1	3.1 (±0.85)	-1.3	18.10	0.23 (±0.04)	0.48
	308.1	2.7 (±0.35)	-3.2	18.11	0.64 (±0.12)	
	309.9	4.0 (±1.15)	-11.5	18.12	1.59 (±0.13)	
	310.9	4.7 (±0.70)	-17.8	18.13	2.10 (±0.27)	
Calcium kaolinite	310.8	3.2 (±0.76)	-7.0	18.13	1.22 (±0.15)	0.17
	312.7	4.8 (±1.07)	-13.3	18.14	1.55 (±0.12)	
	314.1	6.2 (±0.70)	-20.1	18.15	1.84 (±0.09)	
	315.4	6.2 (±1.15)	-22.1	18.16	2.01 (±0.17)	
Magnesium kaolinite	306.6	2.2 (±0.74)	-2.5	18.10	0.59 (±0.13)	0.15
	309.7	4.1 (±1.15)	-7.5	18.12	1.01 (±0.10)	
	310.6	4.5 (±1.06)	-9.6	18.12	1.18 (±0.08)	
	312.0	5.6 (±0.82)	-14.3	18.14	1.43 (±0.07)	

be most efficient (while K^+ the least efficient) in enforcing order through longrange interactions, in, for instance, the outer B and C layers of the Frank and Wen's flickering cluster structural model¹⁰ proposed for electrolyte solutions, and thereby narrowing down the 'entropy gain' of dispersed water within the clay chamber, vis-a-vis bulk water. This should lead to an 'inverse' order of the magnitude of $\hat{Q}_w$ values, i.e. $(\hat{Q}_w)_{K-Ka} > (\hat{Q}_w)_{Ca-Ka} > (\hat{Q}_w)_{Mo-Ka}$ ($Ka \equiv$ Kaolinite matrix), as observed experimentally. Such a trend is also reflected in the $\hat{C}_w$ values, the rise in $\hat{Q}_w$ with temperature being maximum for K-kaolinite clay due to a greater thermal increase in kinetic energy of the clay-bound water in the former as compared to the other two clays.

References

1. J. W. CARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1962, 26, 413.
2. J. W. CARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1962, 26, 417.
3. S. A. TAYLOR and J. W. CARY, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Am.*, 1964, 28, 167.
4. R. P. TRIPATHI and B. P. GHILDYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1978, 26, 313.
5. S. K. SANYAL and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 1071.
6. S. K. SANYAL, B. G. MAITRA and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1983, 31, 464.
7. A. BHATTACHARJYA and S. K. SANYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 1030.
8. A. KATCHALSKY and P. F. CURRAN, "Non-equilibrium Thermodynamics in Biophysics", Harvard Univ. Press, 1965.
9. A. K. MUKHERJEE and S. K. SANYAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, 23, 761.
10. H. S. FRANK and W. Y. WEN, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.

Kinetics of Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction of 1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene with Substituted-anilines

T. MOHAMED IKRAMUDDEEN, N. CHANDRASEKARA and K. RAMARAJAN*

Department of Chemistry, CBM College, Coimbatore-641 042 and

K. A. SUBRAMANIAN

Department of Chemistry, PSG College of Technology, Coimbatore-641 004

Manuscript received 18 July 1988, accepted 9 March 1989

KINETIC behaviour of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene towards amines has been the subject of several publications¹⁻³ in the past. Volumetry, potentiometry and spectrophotometry are some of the techniques adopted to follow the kinetics. Conductometry remained a rarely used technique². The present study aims at investigating the kinetics

of the title reaction in a aqueous dioxane medium by conductometric technique.

Experimental

1-Chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (B.D.H.) was purified by repeated crystallisation from absolute alcohol and dried under reduced pressure before use (m.p. 50 - 1°). The anilines (1 - 7) used (B.D.H.) were purified either by vacuum distillation (liquids) or by crystallisation (solids). Dioxane (AnalaR) was purified following literature procedure⁴.

- 1; X = H
- 2; X = Cl
- 3; X = Br
- 4; X = CH₃

- 5; X = Cl
- 6; X = OH
- 7; X = CH₃

Kinetic measurement : The reaction was followed conductometrically in a bottle type conductivity cell specially designed for this work. Separate solutions of aniline and 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (prepared in 80% aqueous dioxane) were equilibrated at 45 ± 0.05° for 30 min. Equal volume (2 ml) of the above two solutions were mixed in the conductance cell and the rate was followed by measuring the conductance of the solution at regular intervals using a PICO (wire type) conductivity bridge. The rates were followed at least upto 60% reaction. The runs were repeated at 55 and 65°. In order to trap the HCl formed during the reaction, the concentration of the amine was always maintained at exactly twice the concentration of 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene.

All the reactions investigated gave the final substitution products (diphenylamines) in quantitative yield. The products were purified by repeated crystallisation from dioxane-alcohol solvent mixture. Identification was made possible through ir and ¹H nmr spectral data (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Under the conditions employed in the present investigation, the reaction followed a second order kinetics, first order each in nucleophile (aniline) and substrate. The second order rate constants obtained for the various anilines at three different temperatures are reported in Table 2. Table 2 also records the activation parameters calculated following Eyring's equation,

$$\log (k_a/T) = \log (k_B/h) + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{2.303R} - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{2.303R} (1/T)$$

The negative value obtained for the entropy of activation suggests a transition state more organised (less entropic) than the reactants.